

WLCG Token Usage Risk Assessment

[v1.0](#) – April 30, 2026

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1. Introduction

([ToC](#))

The [Token Trust & Traceability](#) (TTT) working group (WG) was started in July 2023 in order to devise and formulate best practice for all aspects of the use of tokens in WLCG and related infrastructures, and inform all parties involved. From June 2025 through March 2026, the TTT WG has carried out the first-ever token usage risk assessment for routine use cases present in WLCG, EGI and OSG. The risk assessment is versioned and will be updated whenever the most recently published version is found to have become inadequate with respect to some important concern.

Compared to the X.509 and VOMS legacy technologies being used since the early days of grid computing, tokens present us with several advantages:

- Tokens can be tuned along 3 orthogonal axes:
 - Lifetime;
 - Scope;
 - Audience.
- Tokens can essentially be hidden from users:
 - Grid tools can be made to obtain the right tokens at the right times.
 - Users will “log into” the grid in a convenient way, typically once per day.
 - Details still need to be worked out and will vary between VOs.

Those advantages come at a price. Instead of using *the* VOMS proxy, grid middleware now has to decide which tokens to use for which operations, with implications for each token's delimiting attributes: audience, scope and lifetime. Their values also determine if a token might be used for several operations, where such reuse can make sense.

On the one hand, tokens can be made usable for very limited purposes, e.g. reading or writing just a single file on a particular SE. On the other hand, by making things easier for users, things may also become easier for misuse, whether by accident or on purpose.

These matters are further discussed in our [CHEP 2024 paper](#).

2. Risk Assessment Procedure and Methodology

([ToC](#))

The members of the TTT WG have various backgrounds that are relevant to grid infrastructure activities, typically with many years of experience in those matters:

- middleware developers;
- operations experts;
- security experts;
- site administrators.

The risk assessment was carried out through 17 meetings from June 2025 through March 2026, each lasting at least 1 hour, with 4 up to 8 participants from a subset of 15 people in the working group. After deciding on the design of the assessment, inspired by previous risk assessments in [WLCCG](#), [EGEE](#), [WISE](#) and [EGI](#) (chapters 6 and 7), we spent a few meetings to identify and classify the risk areas to be covered in our assessment.

Then, spread over the majority of the meetings, for each identified threat we discussed examples and surrounding circumstances. We then made use of a consensus-based blind voting process that allowed each participant in the meeting to cast votes that were only revealed when all votes in a round had been cast. Participants were first asked to rate the likelihood for a given threat to occur, according to a scale from 1 to 5 as explained below. With the likelihood votes revealed, any outliers were discussed, which allowed us to settle on an average likelihood value by consensus each time. Next, participants were asked to rate the typical impact if a given threat were to occur, again according to a scale from 1 to 5, as explained below. With the impact votes revealed, outliers were also discussed here, which also allowed us to settle on an average impact value by consensus. When the votes initially were split between two adjacent values, we typically took the higher rating as a precaution.

A few WG members participated in all meetings, which helped maintain consistency between the ratings of different threats that were considered in different meetings. However, as we gained more insights over the course of the risk assessment, it occurred to us that the early threats might have got different ratings later. Therefore, in the last few meetings we revisited all threats and found we only needed to make a few small adjustments. That said, given that we do not have hard numbers for any of the threats, the assessments need to be based on “guestimates” that may well have to be adjusted in future revisions. We do hope, however, that we have been able to identify the areas where particular attention regarding security is highly recommended.

The following chapters present an executive summary of the risk assessment as well as details for each of the considered threats.

3. Executive Summary and Conclusions

[\(ToC\)](#)

The following table concisely presents the results of the first version of our token usage risk assessment, with ratings from 1 to 5 for Impact and Likelihood, and the Risk being the product of their values:

TR	Description	Impact	Likelihood	Risk
01	AAI Provider Unavailability	3	2	6
02	Rogue Tokens	4	2	8
03	Privilege Escalation	4	2	8
04	Audit Gaps	3	2	6
05	Data Protection	4	3	12
06	Data Access	4	2	8
07	Pilot Submission	2	3	6
08	Ordinary Users: Data Access	2	4	8
09	Ordinary Users: Job Submission	2	4	8
10	Privileged Users: Data Access	4	3	12
11	Privileged Users: Job Submission	4	3	12

We have highlighted the token usage risks with the highest risk values in orange: those would be the ones requiring particular attention regarding security. While further details surrounding those risks and mitigation options are described in dedicated sections below, here we observe that their emergence should not come as a surprise, as they are to a significant extent independent of the type of credential being used. That said, the technology of tokens does provide us with opportunities to reduce those risks and in a future revision of the risk assessment we may well be able then to lower their impact or likelihood values.

From the remaining risks we have highlighted the ones with the highest impact values in yellow. While those risks do have a lower likelihood, their effects would be significant, should they materialize nonetheless. Therefore, also for them it would be good to reduce their impact if possible and otherwise their likelihood even further, if feasible. Mitigation options are suggested in their dedicated sections.

4. Scoring of Likelihood and Impact

([ToC](#))

Inspired by the [WISE Template](#), but scaled 1-5

Likelihood

Guideline	Unlikely to Happen	Happens less than once a year	Happens every few months/more than once a year	Happens every 2-3 months	Happens monthly or more often
Likelihood	1	2	3	4	5

Impact table

	1 "minimal"	2 "minor"	3 "noticeable"	4 "significant"	5 "serious"
Affecting few	1 day disruption / recovery	1 week disruption / recovery	multiple weeks disruption / recovery	1 month +	no recovery
Affecting many		1 day disruption / recovery	1 week disruption / recovery	multiple weeks disruption / recovery	1 month +
Affecting "all"			1 day disruption / recovery	1 week disruption / recovery	multiple weeks disruption / recovery
Affecting Scientific Data	Minimal leak or loss	Minor leak or loss	Noticeable leak or loss	Significant leak or loss	Serious leak or loss
Affecting Personal / Sensitive Data				Leakage of small amount	Leakage of significant amount

Further details follow on the next page.

“Units of Impact”

- Disruption/Recovery Time
- Disruption/Recovery Cost
- Number of users/sites/services affected (rolls into cost)
- For data - nature of data lost/exposed (personal/irrecoverable)
- Reputational damage (decided out of scope for this exercise)

Examples of criteria to consider, depending on the threat:

- Service disruptions affecting groups ranging from few users to a whole VO
 - Example: an infected service that is kept down until it has been reinstalled
- Potential for an incident to spread further across the ecosystem
- Loss of resources (computing, storage, network) due to misuse
 - Loss of data is covered explicitly
- Effects on third parties, in particular through DDoS attacks

5. Token Risk Assessments

[\(ToC\)](#)

Details for the assessments of the considered token risks follow on the next pages.

5.1. AAI Provider Unavailability

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

AAI provider unavailability. This also concerns auxiliary services like HTVault or MyToken. This could prevent public key caches from getting updated. The cause could be any of these: bug, performance issue, configuration error, DoS, issue with underlying service, ...

Asset(s) affected

AAI provider service(s).

Vulnerability

Single instance, no HA, no fallback mechanism

Current mitigation / control

For example, IAM production instances for LHC experiments are HA, with the exception of their DB instances, for which HA deployments may be considered in the future.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
3	2	6

Potential mitigations

- Deploy HA setup.
- Multiple, possibly federated issuers.
- Token minters within VOs.
- Static functionality (e.g. JWKS) hosted in redundant infrastructure.

5.2. Rogue Tokens

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Unauthorized access via rogue tokens (secret leak, vulnerability), i.e. not stolen tokens.

Asset(s) affected

Digital identities, grid resources

Vulnerability

Vulnerability in AAI token validator or secret leak.

Current mitigation / control

For example, the procedure to regenerate the main secrets of the CERN IAM instances has been exercised.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	2	8

Potential mitigations

- Enforce strict token signature validation.
- Test authentication libraries.
- SBOM.
- Procedure to regenerate main secrets.

5.3. Privilege Escalation

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Privilege escalation

Asset(s) affected

Digital identities, data protection, grid resources

Vulnerability

- Incorrect token exchange workflows
- Upscoping
- Incorrect configuration

Current mitigation / control

- Token exchange is a privileged operation that is only enabled for well-managed clients like the FTS.
- In an IAM release > 1.13.4 it will become possible to prevent upscoping on token exchange.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	2	8

Potential mitigations

- Document, test and validate credential workflows.

5.4. Audit Gaps

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Token audit gaps

Asset(s) affected

Data protection, grid resources

Vulnerability

No logs or visibility into token usage, which makes incident response more difficult.

Current mitigation / control

For example, CERN IAM token logs are available to VO admins.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
3	2	6

Potential mitigations

Ensure token audit trail at SP endpoints, do regular audit tests that we can get this trail.

5.5. Data Protection

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Inadequate data protection due to suboptimal use of token features or incorrect configuration of storage or data management services regarding the use of tokens.

Asset(s) affected

Data protection

Vulnerability

Data can too easily be deleted, written, or read, by mistake within a VO workflow or on purpose by a malicious party.

Current mitigation / control

Regular (SAM) tests to check the actual access controls of storage services are already done by CMS.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	3	12

SE services misconfigured regarding authorization have **not** been so uncommon.

Potential mitigations

- Make tokens and the configuration of data namespaces as tight as feasible.
- Run regular (SAM) tests to check the actual access controls of storage services.

5.6. Data Access

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of tokens allowing unauthorized reading, writing, or deletion of data across storage endpoints. This can be due to stolen or leaked tokens.

Asset(s) affected

Data protection

Vulnerability

Stolen tokens could be used to read, write or delete files in a narrow or wide part of the namespace for up to multiple hours or days, depending on token scopes, audience and lifetime.

Current mitigations

For widespread abuse of data, if allowed by the tokens that were obtained, the attacker would need to find some way to obtain the names of other files or directories. Tokens used for reading files **ought to be insufficient for listing directories** on an SE. To be tested for each of the SE flavors, though!

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	2	8

Potential mitigations

- Short lifetimes, which could permit wider scopes and/or audiences.
- Narrow scopes, which could permit longer lifetimes and/or wider audiences.
- Avoid the *storage.modify* scope as much as possible to prevent deletions.

Continued on the next page.

- Restrict tokens to specific SE audiences, which could permit wider scopes and/or longer lifetimes.
- Use the FTS pull mode as much as possible to avoid delegating credentials for writing.
- In an IAM release > 1.13.4 it will become possible to prevent upscoping on token exchange (which already is a privileged operation).

Examples

LHC experiments have employed two complementary token strategies for their FTS workflows, each with its own pros and cons. The FTS is presented with either of these:

1. long-lived, narrowly scoped tokens that are neither exchanged nor renewed;
2. short-lived, more widely scoped tokens that are exchanged and renewed.

Advantages of the first option:

- FTS instances do not have to be given privileges across the VO namespace to permit token exchange. Note: FTS production instances are well-managed services trusted by their VOs.
- Dependence on token exchange and subsequent renewal is avoided.

Advantages of the second option:

- The use of more widely scoped tokens helps reduce the pressure from token acquisition, storage, exchange and renewal, benefiting the data management framework, the FTS and the token issuer.

5.7. Pilot Submission

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of pilot tokens allowing unauthorized payload submission, massive resource abuse (e.g. crypto mining), or indirect data access.

Asset(s) affected

Grid resources, data protection, digital identities

Vulnerability

Computing resources could be abused for crypto mining, sending spam, or attacking other sites. Stolen job tokens might indirectly be used to read or write, but ideally not delete files, possibly in a large part of the namespace for up to multiple days. Rogue jobs would have to imitate pilot jobs to obtain payloads with corresponding data management tokens.

Current mitigation / control

For widespread abuse of data, if allowed by the tokens that were obtained, the attacker would need to find some way to obtain the names of other files or directories. Tokens used for reading files **ought to be insufficient for listing directories** on an SE. To be tested for each of the SE flavors, though!

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
2	3	6

Potential mitigations

- Apply a limit on the number of payloads that a pilot can run.
- Avoid the *storage.modify* scope as much as possible to prevent deletions.
- Give payload tokens narrow scopes.
- Limit payload token lifetimes.
- Restrict payload tokens to specific SE audiences.

5.8. Ordinary Users: Data Access

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of tokens for ordinary users allowing unauthorized reading, writing, or deletion of data limited to a user's personal namespace or specific datasets authorized for that user.

Asset(s) affected

Data protection, digital identities

Vulnerability

Stolen tokens could be used to read, write or remove data in the namespace accessible to the given ordinary user.

Current mitigation / control

Ordinary users only have modification privileges for their own data and possibly for data owned by the analysis groups in which they participate. Ideally only privileged users should be able to delete data owned by an analysis group. In any case it is important to ensure that ordinary users have as few privileges as feasible.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
2	4	8

Potential mitigations

- Narrow scopes
- Short lifetimes
- Specific SE audiences

5.9. Ordinary Users: Job Submission

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of tokens for ordinary users allowing submission of rogue jobs, effective revocation remaining possible via the central task queue.

Asset(s) affected

Grid resources, data protection, digital identities

Vulnerability

Stolen tokens could be used to submit rogue jobs owned by ordinary users.

Current mitigation / control

Any user's jobs can still be removed from the VO's central task queue, which then acts as a revocation channel (running jobs may even be killed).

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
2	4	8

Potential mitigations

- Short lifetimes

5.10. Privileged Users: Data Access

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of tokens for privileged users potentially allowing modification or mass deletion of critical data, possibly leading to wide disruption in the VO.

Asset(s) affected

Data protection, grid resources, digital identities

Vulnerability

Stolen tokens could be used to read, write or remove data in the namespace accessible to the given privileged user.

Current mitigation / control

A VO typically has few privileged users. Such users also ought to be less likely to make potentially costly mistakes, given that they are in charge of significant fractions of the VO's data, grid resource usage and possibly identity management.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	3	12

Potential mitigations

- Narrow scopes
- Short lifetimes
- Specific SE audiences

Comments

To protect a VO against any unwanted mass deletions, it would be good to look into implementing a multi-factor authentication (MFA) scheme for the relevant workflows. A more challenging approach could also be considered: a two-person rule.

5.11. Privileged Users: Job Submission

([ToC](#), [summary](#))

Threat

Compromise / misuse of tokens for privileged users allowing the submission of massive rogue job campaigns, leading to significant resource waste, delays to data processing, or the use of grid resources to launch attacks (e.g. DDoS) against external targets.

Asset(s) affected

Grid resources, digital identities, data protection

Vulnerability

Stolen tokens could be used to submit rogue jobs owned by privileged users.

Current mitigation / control

A VO typically has few privileged users. Such users also ought to be less likely to make potentially costly mistakes, given that they are in charge of significant fractions of the VO's data, grid resource usage and possibly identity management.

Impact, likelihood, risk

Impact	Likelihood	Risk
4	3	12

Potential mitigations

- Short lifetimes

Comments

To protect a VO against rogue job campaigns, it would be good to look into implementing a multi-factor authentication (MFA) scheme for the relevant workflows. A more challenging approach could also be considered: a two-person rule.